

D8.1 Mobile, stable and crisis-resilient career paths of talented young researchers in Europe

forthem.

Fostering Outreach
within European Regions,
Transnational Higher Education
and Mobility

Erasmus + project
European Universities Initiative
FORTHEM Alliance

Beneficiaries, FORTHEM Partner universities

Université Bourgogne Europe

Uniwersytet Opolski

Università degli Studi di Palermo

Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz

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Abstract

Early-stage researchers in Europe continue to face fragmented career pathways, precarious employment conditions, gender inequalities, and uneven recognition of status across Member States. FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers demonstrates that university alliances can mitigate these challenges by piloting mentoring, transferable skills training, flexible mobility, and inclusive research assessment practices. While such initiatives cannot substitute for structural reforms, they provide scalable models that inform the ERA Policy Agenda and show how bottom-up practices and top-down EU action must converge to create more attractive, equitable, and resilient research careers across Europe.

Key words: Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs); Research Careers in Europe; Mobility and Skills Development; Research Assessment Reform; Gender Equality in Academia

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Symbols, Abbreviations, and Acronyms

UBE	Université Bourgogne Europe
UO	Uniwersytet Opolski
UniPa	Università degli Studi di Palermo
JGU	Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz
JYU	Jyväskylän yliopisto
ULBS	Universitatea Lucian Blaga din Sibiu
UV	Universitat de València
UiA	Universitetet i Agder
LU	Latvijas Universitāte
WP	Work Package
EUI	European Universities Initiative
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
ECR / ESR	Early-Career Researcher / Early-Stage Researcher
ERA	European Research Area
EUACDE	European University Association's Council for Doctoral Education
FA4ESR	FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers
FP10	10th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
FORTHEM	Fostering Outreach within European Regions, Transnational Higher Education and Mobility
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HRS4R	Human Resources Strategy for Researchers
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RGP	Researchers Grand Prix

Introduction

The aim of this policy report is to present our reflections and share insights gained through our involvement in FORTHEM Research, Innovation and Transfer Mission (RI&T). One of the mission's key initiatives is FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers (FA4ESR), established in 2022 within the current funding period of FORTHEM Alliance (2022-2026). This initiative builds upon achievements from the first funding phase and the FIT FORTHEM Horizon 2020 project (2021–2023).

Working with the groups of ESRs at FORTHEM partner universities and looking at their needs and specific concern, FORTHEM alliance decided to build the pilot phase of their FA4ESR on the following key topics.

- **Research-related and transversal skills training:** Workshops, master classes, and boot camps focused on enhancing both academic and transferable competencies.
- **Career development and research assessment reform:** Personalized mentoring and coaching aligned with the discussion on evolving assessment models that value diverse outputs and open science practices.
- **Training** in any form must respect the highest standards when it comes to gender equality, diversity, and inclusiveness in their broadest sense.
- **Open science and research visibility through conferences:** Opportunities to publish, present, and collaborate via open platforms and FORTHEM Annual Conference, increasing visibility and impact.
- **Engagement with FORTHEM Labs:** Participation in interdisciplinary research groups tackling real-world challenges like climate change, migration, and digital transformation.
- **Networking and mobility support for ESRs:** International exchanges and cross-institutional collaborations enabling ESRs to expand their professional networks and research exposure.

The overarching framework of the FA4ESR is building on and referring to

- The **European Competence Framework (R1–R4):** Structured skill-building across research, communication, management, and teamwork¹.

1

https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/policy_library/towards_a_european_framework_for_research_careers_final.pdf (accessed: 31 July 2025), published in 2011.

- The **European Competence Framework for Researchers**: Support for the development of researchers' transversal skills, and is fostering inter-sectoral careers².
- Researcher **Development Lifecycle Models**: Clear pathways through training, mentorship, and institutional support³.
- DIOSI **Doctoral Learning Model**: Holistic professional growth integrating research training, self-management, and transferable skills⁴.
- **Quadruple/Quintuple Helix Model**: Active engagement between academia, industry, policymakers, society, and the environment⁵.

Following these approaches and key ideas, in 2024, we also submitted a proposal under Horizon Europe, titled "FORTHM Talent Hub", which focused on support for early-stage researchers (ESRs), though it was not selected for funding. FORTHM Talent Hub project aimed to enhance the excellence and competitiveness of Early-Stage Researchers in the European job market by implementing the ERA Policy Agenda's Action 4 and the New Charter for Researchers. The project focuses on creating inter-sectoral talent ecosystems to maximize knowledge creation and application through EU funding synergies. It seeks to identify the needs of regional research and innovation labor markets by engaging non-academic partners, ESRs, and partner universities across the FORTHM area.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en (accessed: 31 July 2025).

³ For example:

- Researcher Development Framework ([RDF](#)).

- Research Skill Development (RSD) Framework: Tiala, S., Loy, K. (2024). Research-Oriented University Instruction: The Research Skill Development Framework and Communities of Practice. In: Willison, J. (eds) Research Thinking for Responsive Teaching. SpringerBriefs in Education. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-6679-0_5.

- Researcher Career Development & Leadership Frameworks (UKRI and IU-based): [ESRC-011222-FitForTheFuture-EvidenceReview.pdf](#) (access 31 July 2025), mainly referring to the Social Sciences and Humanities.

⁴ The concept was developed by the YUFE Alliance in a Horizon 2020 Project: Grant agreement ID: 101006318. FORTHM is not copying the programme but instead inspired by the approach.: [Developing and Implementing hands-on training on Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers | DIOSI | Projekt | Fact Sheet | H2020 | CORDIS | European Commission](#).

⁵ See for example: Machado, H.P.V., Sartori, R. & Rosa, P.F.M. Beyond the Triple Helix Model: Scientific Production on the Quadruple and Quintuple Helix. *J Knowl Econ* **16**, 5758–5791 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-02026-4> (access 31 July 2025). Following the ideas of the Triple Helix, Quadruple Helix, or finally Quintuple Helix model, it is quite clear, that the future design of a training framework for early-stage researchers (ESRs) must reflect a dynamic, multi-actor innovation ecosystem that integrates academic, societal, governmental, industrial, and environmental dimensions

Objectives and Methodology

Based on six years of experience within FORTHEM Alliance and three years of activities under the FA4ESR (FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers), this policy paper presents our observations, reflections, and recommendations for future European policy-making in the field of academic careers. We focus in particular on the following key areas:

- The stability and/or precarity of the professional status of early-stage researchers (ESRs) across the EU;
- The role of international mobility in enhancing working conditions for talented young researchers and strengthening the overall research capacity of the European Research Area;
- The identification of strategic institutions, tools, and areas within academia where structural changes could significantly improve the attractiveness of academic careers;
- Proposals for innovative tools and approaches in academic training, support, mentoring, and assessment, inspired by initiatives developed within FA4ESR.

The authors of this paper are academic experts with experience working in various European higher education systems. They bring diverse national perspectives, extensive international collaboration backgrounds, and—most importantly—three years of joint work focused on building and sustaining an international academic environment for ESRs. This work has involved PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers from nine countries within FORTHEM Alliance.

Our recommendations are grounded in practical experience gained through the delivery of online training sessions, masterclasses, in-person workshops, a mentoring programme, the launch of a new academic journal, organization of conference panels for ESRs, experimentation with new forms of scientific communication, and efforts to integrate doctoral schools across nine partner countries. These activities were accompanied by numerous consultations with representatives from the European Commission, the European University Association, COARA, national and regional bodies, and university leaders responsible for supporting ESRs.

Finally, and crucially, our work has involved direct engagement with several hundred early-stage researchers from the nine FORTHEM Alliance universities: Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (Germany), Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu (Romania), Université Bourgogne Europe (France), University of Opole (Poland), University of Jyväskylä (Finland), University of Agder (Norway), University of Valencia (Spain), University of Latvia (Riga), and the University of Palermo (Italy). We support our

recommendations with relevant scientific literature, European and national documents and regulations, and unstructured interviews.

The structure of this paper is as follows. In the introductory and methodological section, we explain our main objectives and describe the approach and methods used in developing the paper. In the analytical part, we discuss the current challenges facing academia in the European Union, drawing on key policy documents and relevant scientific literature. This section serves as the diagnostic part of the paper. The following section presents an analysis of the activities carried out by FA4ESR, with a focus on how they relate to the paper's aims. In the final section, we summarize our findings, reflecting on how our approach has influenced the situation of early-stage researchers (ESRs) within FORTHEM Alliance and its potential impact on the European Research Area. We also offer recommendations—highlighting which aspects of our experience could be valuable for other university alliances and suggesting how the ERA policy agenda might be enhanced based on our work.

Policy Review and Academic Job Market Analysis

European Union is gaining a lot of effort in supporting ESRs. The European Commission has shown interest in higher education since the time of its third administration, the Ortolí Commission (1973–1977)⁶. During this period, the German-British sociologist and political scientist Ralph Dahrendorf served as the Commissioner for Research and Education. Established in the 2000, European Research Area, focused since the very beginning on academic and scientific careers. In the years that followed, the European Union introduced many initiatives focused on higher education. A comprehensive set of EU policy and legislative instruments supports researchers and young researchers. These include, among others:

- Commission Recommendation 2005/251/EC of 11 March 2005 on the European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers,
- Directive (EU) 2021/1883 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2021 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purpose of highly qualified employment, and repealing Council Directive 2009/50/EC (OJ L 382, 28.10.2021, p. 1),

⁶ K. Zuba, *Europeanisation as an opportunity structure for higher education*. In: A. Frame, B. Curyto (eds.) *The European Universities Initiative and the 'Euro-Internationalisation' of European Higher Education*. Routledge, 2025, p. 37.

- Directive (EU) 2016/801 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of research, studies, training, voluntary service, pupil exchange schemes or educational projects and au pairing (OJ L 132, 21.5.2016, p. 21).
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions ‘European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience’, COM (2020) 274 final,
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – A Union for Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, COM (2020) 152 final,
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions ‘A new ERA for Research and Innovation’, COM (2020) 628 final,
- Council Recommendation (EU) 2021/2122 of 26 November 2021 on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe (OJ L 431, 2.12.2021, p. 1),
- Council conclusions on the European Universities initiative – Bridging higher education, research, innovation and society: Paving the way for a new dimension in European higher education (OJ C 221, 10.6.2021, p. 14),
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on a European strategy for universities, COM (2022) 16 final,
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – A New European Innovation Agenda, COM (2022) 332 final,
- Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 of 2 December 2022 on the guiding principles for knowledge valorisation (OJ L 317, 9.12.2022, p. 141),
- Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 of 2 December 2022 on the guiding principles for knowledge valorisation (OJ L 317, 9.12.2022, p. 141),

- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions ‘Attracting skills and talent to the EU’, COM (2022) 657 final,
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions ‘Harnessing talent in Europe’s regions’, 17 January 2023, COM (2023) 32 final,

In the first ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024, the ERA action 4 aimed to improve research careers in Europe by enhancing working conditions, addressing skills mismatches, and supporting mobility. It includes developing a European framework, promoting best practice exchange, and strengthening tools like EURAXESS and ResearchComp to attract and retain talent across sectors, disciplines, and international borders. While this action was relevant to researchers at all career stages, early-stage researchers are central to its success. However, it is notable that within the ERA Policy Agenda document, early-stage researchers are explicitly mentioned only once—in Action 14, relating to the European City of Science initiative (p. 17).

The perspective of the FA4ESRs in the light of the new ERA policy agenda for 2025 – 2027 evaluated against their core focus topics:

- 1) The new Agenda (2025–27) deepens their ambitions related to academic careers by embedding a long-term structural policy to make research careers more attractive, sustainable, and mobile, with tailored actions to support career flexibility and resilience for ESRs. The major objectives refer to comparability of careers, recruitment, skills development, investments, talent circulation and interdisciplinary careers and synergies with other ERA policy priorities (all Tasks of the FA4ESR).
- 2) The new agenda elevates equity in open science as a specific ERA action: enhancing capacity-building, skills, infrastructure access, and recognition systems to ensure all researchers—including ESRs—can participate fully. The main focus is on breaking down barriers, supporting skills development, finances and recognition. (Current FORTHEM Task 8.3)
- 3) The new policy formalizes gender equality and inclusiveness as a structural policy, with an intersectional approach and emphasis on system-wide mainstreaming in R&I environments, such as Gender Equality Plans, intersectoral approaches, and fairer recruitment to under-represented and marginalised group (especially current FORTHEM Task 8.2, 8.4).

4) The 2025–27 Agenda builds on previous efforts related to research assessment reform by adding it as well as a structural policy, and is linking it with knowledge valorisation (i.e., stronger ties between academia and business) to ensure ESRs' contribution, such as in industry collaborations or when it comes to societal impact, are fairly recognized. (Current FORTHEM Task 8.2, 8.5 and many action in WP7)

This rather long list of documents and actions undertaken has one diagnosis of the situation: despite all the efforts of EC, early career researchers in Europe face precarious working conditions, limited long-term employment opportunities, and insufficient social protection. Career paths are still often linear, narrowly focused on academia, and do not support inter-sectoral mobility. Challenges include gender inequality, skills mismatches, and administrative or legal barriers that restrict mobility and career progression.

What is proposed in the Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe, is establishing a European framework for research careers to make them more attractive, inclusive, and sustainable. Key measures include: improving employment conditions, promoting open and merit-based recruitment, ensuring social protection, encouraging mobility across sectors and countries, supporting career diversification, and developing tools like ResearchComp, EURAXESS, and the ERA Talent Platform to better support skills development and career management.

Doctoral education and postdoctoral research in Europe

In Europe, still around 19 % of researchers, especially those at an early stage in their career, are working under precarious conditions⁷, even though the European Charter for Researchers⁸ defines key principles for fair recruitment, ethical standards, and supportive working conditions in research careers, with a strong focus on transparency, mobility, and skills development for early-stage researchers (ESRs). As part of the EU's Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), it aims to promote career stability and institutional accountability across Europe. FORTHEM Alliance is fully committed to these principles, yet faces ongoing challenges in implementing cross-institutional standards due to the diverse national frameworks and starting points of its member universities.

⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>, page 190 (access 4.8.2025).

⁸ COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION of 18 December 2023 on a [European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe](#) (C/2023/1640), pages 18 – 29 Annex II (access 4.8.2025).

Status of doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers

The status of PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers continues to vary widely, including across the FORTHEM countries France, Germany, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Spain, as well the Nordic countries Finland and Norway. While in some countries, like Germany and France, PhD candidates are increasingly regarded as early-stage researchers and are often employed under fixed-term contracts that entitle them to salaries, social security, and other employment benefits, sometimes the Nordic countries like Finland and Norway even go one step further treating PhD candidates as full staff members, sometimes even with full-time working contracts, and thus serving as role models for more secure and supportive research careers: they are employed by universities, receive regular salaries, and benefit from full access to health insurance, pensions, and paid parental leave. By contrast, in countries such as Italy, Latvia, and Romania, PhD candidates are more often classified as students and receive stipends or grants, often without social protection or employment contracts. In those countries, the same applies even for postdoctoral researchers, an issue widely discussed for example in reports and policy briefs provided by the OECD⁹ as well as in the European University Association's doctoral education reports.¹⁰ It is mentioned, that postdoctoral researchers also experience varied working conditions: while Germany, Finland, and Norway sometimes offer structured postdoctoral programs or support structures with transparent career development frameworks, postdocs in Latvia Spain and Poland still face short-term contracts and limited institutional support; sometimes even under a not fully definition on what a postdoctoral researcher is. The discussion about new forms of research assessment has significantly advanced the topic in recent years. As Science Europe already stated in 2021¹¹, the main goal is to recognize a broader range of roles - especially the contributions of early career researchers in collaborative and team-based research—thereby increasing the attractiveness of research careers for talented individuals. The harmonization of status definitions, support mechanisms, career development measures, and permeable structures across Europe would be important steps in this process. Despite policy convergence efforts under the European Research Area, major disparities persist and become apparent even more when establishing cross-border collaboration aiming at offering training and support to those groups of people not coming with the same needs and possibilities and not open to participation equally to offers made¹².

⁹ For example: Reducing the precarity of academic research careers, [OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers No 113 \(2021\)](#), page 10 (access 4.8.2025)

¹⁰ Simon Marti and Ana-Maria Peneo, [2025 SURVEY – REPORT I: Doctoral education in Europe today: enhanced structures and practices for the European knowledge society](#) (access 4.8.2025)

¹¹ Science Europe. (2021). Empowering researchers with a thriving research system integrated in society. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726893>, page 3 (access 4.8.2025)

¹² See also [FIT FORTHEM ERA Policy Brief No. 2](#) (2023) page 4 (access 4.8.2025).

Gender Inequalities in Academic Careers in Europe: Patterns, Policies, and the Case of FORTHEM Countries

Despite major advances in access to higher education, gender disparities persist across the academic career trajectory in FORTHEM countries. On European level, women represent nearly half of all doctoral graduates¹³, with significantly lower averages already among the graduates in STEM ranging from around 27% in Germany and Spain to about 42.5% in Romania, just showcasing the differences between FORTHEM countries¹⁴.

Tab. 1: Women doctoral graduates as of 2021

Country	Percentage 2021
France	44%
Germany	45,9%
Italy	48,9%
Spain	49,0%
Latvia	50,1% ¹⁵
Norway	51,0%
Finland	52,3%
Poland	53,4%
Romania	54,5%
average for FORTHEM countries:	49,90%

Source: European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>, page 46 Fig. 2.1 (access 4.8.2025).

¹³ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>, page 232 (access 4.8.2025).

¹⁴ EUROSTAT News Articles, 8 March 2024, Women totalled almost a third of STEM graduates in 2021

¹⁵ Slightly higher number in Latvian Public Media, [Latvia leads EU on women doing doctoral studies](#), mentioning a percentage of 59,6% for Latvia and a European average of 48,5 % at doctoral level. For those higher numbers also see European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>, page 238 Fig. 6.1 with reference to staff in Grade A-D (access 4.8.2025).

The overview clearly indicates that doctoral education has reached near parity in many contexts. However, this relative equality erodes at subsequent stages. At the postdoctoral level, women continue to constitute a substantial share of researchers, with percentages varying between 39,8% (Spain) and 50% in most FORTHEM countries. Latvia (59%) and Romania (54,7 %) even show a higher female majority in this staff group¹⁶. Yet the postdoc phase remains a structurally vulnerable career stage, characterized by short-term contracts, high mobility demands, and limited progression prospects. The underrepresentation of women becomes most pronounced at the level of professorships or even leadership of institution. For example, in Germany (23,8%), Italy (27%), and Poland (28,2%), women hold fewer than 30% of full professorships. Leading positions are taken by Romania (51,4 %) and Latvia (43,5%), but still a consistent drop is observed between the postdoctoral and professorial ranks. This points to entrenched structural barriers in promotion systems, implicit bias in hiring, and a lack of institutional accountability.

This pattern illustrates the well-documented "leaky pipeline" in academic careers. While European frameworks such as Horizon Europe have introduced mechanisms like mandatory Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), national implementation varies significantly. Without binding policies, transparent hiring procedures, and targeted interventions - particularly during the postdoctoral phase - gender parity in academia remains elusive.

Integration of PhD graduates into the labor market

Despite the precarious working conditions mentioned above for researchers in academia, PhD graduates across Europe demonstrate consistently high employment outcomes. OECD data show that the employment rate for individuals holding a doctoral degree is approximately 92%¹⁷. In some EU member states, this figure is even higher. Longitudinal studies further confirm that nearly all doctoral graduates secure employment within a few years many outside academia, particularly in industry, the public sector, or civil society organizations¹⁸. There is a lack of up-to-date official data on the salaries of early-stage researchers. The last comprehensive analysis covering all EU-28 Member States,

¹⁶ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>, page 236 (access 4.8.2025).

¹⁷ Eva Hnatkova, Iryna Degtyarova, Margaux Kersschot, Julia Boman, Labour market perspectives for PhD graduates in Europe, *European Journal of Education, Research, Development and Policy* 57,3, 2022, page 396. DOI: [10.1111/ejed.12514](https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12514).

¹⁸ Boman, J., Barrioluengo, M.S. & van der Weijden, I. Determinants of the career pathways of doctorate holders: Evidence from eight European universities. *Higher Education* 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-025-01418-y>.

conducted in 2016¹⁹, revealed striking differences—PhD candidates in Poland received an average salary nearly ten times lower than their counterparts in the United Kingdom. Since then, the situation has evolved; however, a substantial pay gap between the western and eastern regions of the European Union remains. For example, university professors in Germany can expect to earn at least twice as much as their counterparts in Poland, even after adjusting for differences in the cost of living.

These findings underline the strong integration of graduates with a PhD into European labour markets. Still the transition between academia and the non-academic labor market sometimes is perceived as some kind of a stigma in some areas and people find themselves in some kind of dilemma choosing between the sometimes precarious working conditions in academia and better job opportunities outside academia, that in many cases, will not even be necessarily linked to their educational background.

Three key questions FORTHEM is particularly interested in, when it comes to the further development of their Academy for Early-Stage Researchers.

1. Are mobility experiences during the time of doctoral education mandatory or at least of a major benefit for a smooth transition into the labor market after PhD? And does the same answer apply both for the academic and the non-academic labor market?
2. What kind of training is need besides research-based training in terms of transferrable skills and in contribution to the newly proclaimed Union of Skills Europe advocates for?
3. Are we currently offering an education at the universities that is still preparing the candidates best for labor market conditions in and outside academia?

Doctoral Mobility: Mandatory or least beneficial?

Over the last decades researchers faced increasing expectations when it comes to international mobility experiences. While only few institutions would go that far to make it mandatory for PhD students to go abroad while working on their thesis, mobility during doctoral studies is increasingly seen as a significant advantage. Mobility provides substantial benefits fostering wider research networks, enhancing productivity, and serving as a strong catalyst for career progression, especially in academia²⁰. For the non-academic sector there is less evidence, but it seems that international mobility

¹⁹ B. Torrisi, Asymmetric Salary and Uniformity of Academic Positions at Universities in the EU28, *Open Access Library Journal* vol. 3, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1103198>

²⁰ Bojica, A.M., Olmos-Peñuela, J. & Alegre, J. A cross-country configurational approach to international academic mobility: exploring mobility effects on academics' career progression in EU countries. *Higher Education* 86, 1081–1105, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-022-00963-0> .

benefits both academic and non-academic research careers, especially where regional innovation ecosystems are strong and employers actively collaborate with universities²¹.

Even though there are no doubts related to the benefits of mobility experiences, of course during, but even after the Covid 19 Pandemic universities experience decreased willingness of students and researchers at an early stage in their career to agree to long-term mobility plans, while more flexible programmes, hybrid work models, or multi-site setups instead of classic one-location fellowships are preferred²². FORTHEM has experienced that mobility programmes for up to 3 months for postdoctoral researchers were not in such high demand as expected at the stage of setting-up the funding scheme in 2022. The reasons for objections towards research-stays abroad can be different, many people, also when tackling the topic of mobility in trainings offered by FORTHEM, mentioned economic reasons, family issues, not clarified issues related to social security or travel restriction in case of new times of crisis like during the COVID-19 Pandemic²³. Further developing mobility actions for PhDs and PostDocs need to take this new trend into account.

Are universities preparing PhDs and PostDocs best for the fast-changing world in the labor market both in terms of research as well as transferrable skills?

FORTHEM believes that we already demonstrate clear potential and strategic coherence in preparing early-stage researchers, with solid structures for training, internationalization, and grant readiness with a strategic focus on career preparation, high-level proposal writing trainings, and policy alignment. But we are also aware that we need to do more to make our success stories more visible, and thus demonstrate effectiveness or return on investment. Also, institutional integration can be improved to make FORTHEM really a model for cross-border research career development. The same applies when it comes to the full recognition of multiple career pathways, and multiple contributions to excellent research (Open Science, Knowledge Transfer, Science Communication, and group achievements).

When it comes to the general preparedness of universities making people ready for different labor market scenarios, we think that many European universities are making strides, but there is still room

²¹ Boman, J., Barrioluengo, M.S. & van der Weijden, I. Determinants of the career pathways of doctorate holders: Evidence from eight European universities. *Higher Education* 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-025-01418-y>.

²² Zayim-Kurtay, M., Kaya-Kasicki, S., Kondakci, Y. *et al.* Im/mobility in a disruptive time: the impact of Covid-19 on the size and directional flow of international student mobility. *Center for Migration Studies* 13, 15 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-025-00431-5> (focus on students).

²³ For obstacles in general also see: Informations und Mobilitätsverhalten. Eine weltweite Befragung internationaler Nachwuchs wissenschaftler, *Schriftenreihe Hochschulmarketing 17, DAAD 2019*.

for improvement. Even though European Commission is promoting the integration of transferrable skills training in doctoral and postdoctoral education, quite often, in regular, non-EU funded training curricula, those trainings are quite often more optional than regularly embedded²⁴.

According to a 2025 survey conducted by the European University Association's Council for Doctoral Education (EUA-CDE), doctoral schools across Europe institutionalize transferable skills training and career development offerings at scale. The survey reports a significant rise in structured skills provision from 41% in 2017/18 to 89% in 2025 demonstrating that universities are increasingly embedding training opportunities such as career orientation, interdisciplinary interaction, and transferable skills into doctoral programs. This marks a clear institutional shift beyond optional or ad hoc approaches²⁵. This cultural change is key, because labour markets evolve more rapidly than traditional academic structures. Universities must ensure that doctoral training equips candidates not only with deep disciplinary expertise but also with adaptable, transferable skills that support agile career transitions across sectors.

There is also no straightforward answer to the question of which academic system best supports scientific excellence. According to major university rankings in Europe, such as the 2024 Shanghai Ranking, the top 100 includes universities from 10 European countries, 7 of which are EU members: Germany, France, the Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark, Belgium, and Finland²⁶. Institutions from Western Europe and Scandinavia tend to rank higher than those from Southern and Eastern Europe. This difference cannot be explained solely—or even primarily—by funding levels or career structures. In a noteworthy article published in *Higher Education* in 2019²⁷, the authors argue that the attractiveness of academic careers for early-stage researchers depends on multiple factors. These include salary, quality of life, career prospects, the balance between research and teaching responsibilities, the organization of research activities, availability of funding, and the likelihood of collaborating with highly qualified colleagues. The authors examined 11 countries (10 European countries and the United States) and highlighted differences in the academic job attractiveness index. They also explored how these differences relate to research performance. According to their analysis,

²⁴ EUA Council for Doctoral Educations: Alexander Hasgall, Bregt Saenen, Lidia Borrell-Damian et al, [Doctoral education in Europe today](#): approaches and institutional structures (2008) (access 15.08.2025).

²⁵ EUA Council for Doctoral Educations: Simon Marti, Ana-Maria Peneoasu [Doctoral education in Europe today](#): enhanced structures and practices for the European knowledge society (2025) (access 15.8.2025).

²⁶ <https://www.shanghairanking.com/rankings/arwu/2024> (accessed: 24 July, 2025)

²⁷ J. Janger, D.F.J. Campbell, A. Strauss, Attractiveness of jobs in academia: a cross-country perspective, *Higher Education* 2019, 78: 991-1010.

the Netherlands, the United States, and Switzerland are the most successful in linking academic career systems with high levels of scientific excellence²⁸.

FORTHEM Academy: Empowering Early-Stage Researchers Across Europe

FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers of FORTHEM Alliance focuses on creating a comprehensive support system for ESRs, including doctoral candidates and postdoctoral researchers, across nine European partner universities. Led by Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz (JGU), the Academy runs from the beginning of 2023. Its main aim is to strengthen the academic and professional development of young researchers through structured training, international collaboration, open science engagement, and improved career pathways.

One of the central goals of FA4ESR was to offer targeted training for approximately 500 ESRs each year. This included the development of transferable skills, guidance in applying for research grants, and support for building networks within and beyond academia. The training programme featured over 30 one-day workshops and masterclasses, week-long training sessions, and various forms of individual support such as secondments, cotutelle opportunities, and hybrid mentoring schemes.

A key part of FA4ESR was the promotion of open science practices. This is achieved through several initiatives, including the launch of *FORTHEM Journal*, Researchers Grand Prix, research video projects, and annual open science competitions. These activities gave ESRs the chance to share their research with wider audiences and to practice new methods of scientific communication.

FA4ESR also places a strong emphasis on international mobility and collaboration. Graduate schools and research centres from FORTHEM universities are connected through joint workshops, interdisciplinary schools, session for ESRs on FORTHEM Conference, and short-term mobility schemes. These efforts helped to create a common academic space across the alliance. Another important element was the FORTHEM mentoring programme, which supported different levels of mentoring: senior researchers for postdocs, postdocs for doctoral students, and doctoral students for undergraduates. The programme combined online and face-to-face formats, including training sessions and annual calls for new participants.

²⁸ Ibidem, p. 1003.

In addition, FA4ESR addresses the need for reform in academic assessment practices. It involved research into evaluation systems across partner countries and produced policy briefs and recommendations to promote more inclusive and effective assessment criteria, aligned with European Commission goals. Finally, FA4ESR developed a long-term funding strategy to ensure sustainability. This includes plans to apply for Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) fellowships, doctoral networks, and other third-party funding. The Academy also supports ESRs interested in entrepreneurship by connecting them with European networks²⁹.

Our efforts to establish the Academia were relatively innovative. Coming from diverse academic backgrounds and working within a project-based framework, we contributed a variety of perspectives, a strong intrinsic motivation for change, and a degree of independence from bureaucratic constraints. In this context, facilitative leadership—rather than hierarchical control—proved essential within the public university setting³⁰.

Below we present our reflections on the activities carried out within the Academia over the past three years, focusing on the effect on ESRs and the feedback we got. Leadership roles for specific tasks were assigned based on the expertise of each partner institution. For instance, the University of Opole, with its experience in publishing open-access online journals, was responsible for launching *FORTHEM Journal*. Johannes Gutenberg University (JGU), known for its expertise in third-party funding, led the MSCA training initiative. Despite these task allocations, all activities were implemented jointly by the Academia team.

During the project, we engaged in ongoing discussions and regularly adapted our actions to the actual needs of Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs), as well as to our capacities, expertise, and the outcomes of earlier project phases. It is important to note that the structure of the Academia—formally a work package within a four-year project—was initially designed during the proposal phase, which did not always reflect the real and evolving needs of the ESRs.

As with most funded projects, there were certain constraints: tasks could not be skipped without justification. In balancing the expectations of our target group—by responding to their real needs—

²⁹ FORTHEM – Fostering outreach within European regions, transnational higher education and mobility (application form – technical description; part B)

³⁰ K. Molek-Kozakowska, R. Geisler, De-bureaucratising organisational culture at a public university: A mixed-method study of the implementation of a liberal arts programme, *Higher Education Quarterly* 2020, 74; pp. 410-425. <http://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12262>

and the commitments made to our funder, we often went beyond what was originally planned in the proposal when adjustments were necessary.

Training activities

FORTHem MasterClass is a structured 3-day training aimed at supporting early-career researchers in preparing high-quality proposals for the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship. It includes an introduction to the funding scheme, practical guidance on proposal writing, and feedback from former evaluators and successful applicants. Participants engage in interactive sessions, present their project ideas for expert review, and receive individual support from FORTHem universities. The training is designed for researchers with a defined project idea and host institution, but also for potential supervisors and those simply curious about the funding scheme as a tool to increase their opportunities for career development.

Between 2023 and 2025, FORTHem MasterClass for MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships faced several challenges in ensuring balanced participation and engagement across the alliance. While the fully online format increased accessibility, it also limited opportunities for peer exchange, informal mentoring, and deeper interaction—especially for early-stage researchers (ESRs). The decision to adopt an online-only model was based on diverging PhD schedules³¹ across partner universities and significant differences in participants' prior knowledge of the MSCA scheme. This format aimed to lower access barriers by allowing flexible participation and module selection based on individual needs. However, participants and organizers noted additional obstacles to physical mobility, including Easter breaks, varying institutional calendars, limited Erasmus+ funding, differences in PhD candidate status across countries, availability of trainers, and language barriers. These factors made centralized in-person events impractical and highlighted the need for future improvements in interactivity and follow-up support within partner institutions.

Despite these challenges, the MasterClass had a demonstrably positive impact as a training initiative. It reached 171 participants—far exceeding the originally planned 48—and achieved high satisfaction ratings, with an average of 87–91%, equivalent to a “very good” evaluation. Participants praised the clarity and structure of the modules, particularly those focused on the funding scheme, proposal writing, and the evaluation process. The flexible, modular format allowed attendees to tailor their

³¹ Despite the funding scheme being primarily intended for postdoctoral researchers, approximately 30% of participants (to be confirmed) were PhD candidates, most of them in the final phase of their studies. After completing their PhD, many prospective applicants face unclear institutional status—no longer students, yet often without a formal employment contract—making them ineligible for staff support and limiting access to mobility or training funds.

learning to their existing knowledge levels. Interactive project pitch sessions were seen as especially valuable for peer learning and constructive feedback. The inclusion of former MSCA fellows provided motivating, experience-based insights, while practical advice on clear language and alignment with MSCA criteria was frequently noted as helpful. Mentimeter evaluations confirmed that the training significantly increased participants' confidence in preparing competitive proposals. Despite its online nature, the MasterClass created an inclusive and supportive learning environment, particularly beneficial for those with limited mobility or institutional support.

FORTHEM MasterClass enhances the employability and skills of early-stage researchers (ESRs) by strengthening their competencies in grant writing, project design, and research communication—key assets for careers within and beyond academia. Structured training in competitive funding schemes like the MSCA has been shown to improve researchers' success rates, career planning, and project management skills. Exposure to evaluator expectations, peer feedback, and interdisciplinary practices fosters autonomy and increases confidence. These elements are essential for ESRs navigating today's diverse research and innovation landscapes³².

Another component of our training activities is a series of online workshops designed to develop new skills among the Early-Stage Researchers. These workshops focus on fostering an entrepreneurial mindset, improving scientific communication, and increasing knowledge of research funding schemes. Each training session takes the form of a 2–4-hour online workshop, offered free of charge upon registration. While primarily targeted at FORTHEM ESRs, the sessions are open to all interested participants.

The content is delivered by experts from our partner universities, without the involvement of external trainers. The choice of training topics is made by the respective partner responsible for the session.

To date, nine sessions have been organized. We have observed a high level of interest among ESRs, with more than 100 registrations for several events. In three cases, the number of registrations was lower, including one session that reached its maximum participant limit. The drop-out rate has ranged from 30% to 60%. Post-training evaluations were completed by approximately 50% fewer participants

³² **European Commission, DG Research & Innovation. (2020).** *Support data collection and analysis concerning mobility patterns and career paths of researchers* ([MORE4 Final Report](#)). (access 31 July 2025); **European Research Executive Agency (REA). (2025, May 16).** [End-of-fellowship and follow-up questionnaire results: MSCA skills development and career trajectories of fellows funded under Horizon 2020. Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\) News.](#) European Commission. Full report on [results of msca end of fellowship evaluation questionnaires-NC0125050ENN.pdf](#) (access 31 July 2025).

than those who attended. Evaluation response rates were higher when surveys were conducted at the end of the session, rather than sent by email afterward.

We consider the drop-out rate a common characteristic of online academic events. Based on our experience from the nine sessions, we are now better equipped to estimate actual participation and prepare trainers accordingly. We have also observed that hybrid-format sessions tend to attract greater interest. One such session—focused on "European and American Academia after the Trump Election"—drew approximately 180 participants, including 125 online. This was nearly three times the average participation rate, suggesting that both the format and topical relevance can significantly enhance engagement.

Promoting open science communication

As part of this action, we are engaged in several key activities:

- Establishing and editing *FORTHEM Journal*
- Organizing the annual competition for early-stage researchers (ESRs), the "Researchers' Grand Prix"
- Creating video abstracts
- Establishing a prize for young researchers working on open science and citizen science projects
- Organizing special sessions for ESRs during the annual FORTHEM Alliance conference

Launching a new scientific journal within the framework of the project has been a particularly challenging task. While traditional scientific communication still relies heavily on established journals with Impact & Policy Recommendations Factors—especially in STEM fields—we encountered additional difficulties. These included the journal's multidisciplinary scope and the question of its target audience: Should it be limited to ESRs within FORTHEM Alliance, or open to a broader community? We chose the latter, reflecting the principles of open science, even though this extended beyond the project's original scope.

At the time of writing, the journal is still in its pre-incubation phase. Following extensive outreach and a first call for papers, we are currently reviewing and preparing to publish the initial set of submissions, which include academic articles, essays, and communication reports. So far, 23 ESRs have submitted papers as authors, and 13 are involved as journal editors. Involving ESRs as co-editors alongside senior researchers is a particularly innovative aspect of this initiative. It offers significant potential for building

both the competencies and confidence of early-career researchers. While there are some existing examples of ESRs serving as journal editors³³, this practice has not yet become standard in academic publishing.

We see considerable potential in this initiative. Although the direct impact of the Journal—measured, for example, by the number of published papers—may be relatively limited, the indirect benefits are significant. One such benefit is the ‘learning by doing’ experience gained through editorial work, which offers added value for the career development of early-stage researchers (ESRs). By working alongside senior editors—similar to a mentoring arrangement—and engaging with submitted manuscripts, ESRs can develop essential academic skills in a supportive environment. This includes understanding publication ethics, exploring various forms of scientific communication, and gaining insights into the publishing process from behind the scenes.

Recent studies indicate that younger researchers generally have a more favorable view of open access publishing. They perceive it as offering more opportunities to disseminate their work and to build their academic profiles more quickly. Many also make use of social media and diverse platforms to increase their visibility. However, due to their relatively limited experience, they tend to rely more heavily on traditional trust indicators such as journal impact factors³⁴. It is also worth noting that early-career researchers are now more frequently invited to serve as peer reviewers than was common a decade ago³⁵.

Researchers Grand Prix

The Researchers Grand Prix (RGP) is a science communication initiative aimed at PhD candidates, challenging them to present their research in an engaging and comprehensible manner within a strict four-minute time limit. Originally developed by the Research Council of Norway in 2010, the format emphasizes clarity, accessibility, and societal relevance. Participants receive dedicated training in content development, visual presentation, and stage performance, with the goal of enhancing their ability to communicate complex scientific ideas to a non-specialist audience.

³³ Marshall, H., & Fernandes, M. (2021). Early-career researchers shaping publishing strategy. *Learned Publishing*, 34(4), 675-678.

³⁴ Nicholas, D., Jamali, H. R., Watkinson, A., Herman, E., Tenopir, C., Volentine, R., ... & Levine, K. (2015). Do younger researchers assess trustworthiness differently when deciding what to read and cite and where to publish?. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 5(2): 45-63.

³⁵ Agathokleous, E. (2021). Engaging in scientific peer review: tips for young reviewers. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 32(6), 2249-2254.

In 2023, the University of Agder introduced the RGP concept to FORTHEM Alliance at a communication workshop in Opole. One year later, in November 2024, the first international edition of FORTHEM Researchers Grand Prix was held in Kristiansand, Norway. PhD candidates from six universities participated: Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Université Bourgogne Europe, University of Opole, University of Jyväskylä, University of Latvia, and the University of Agder. The winning presentation, focused on artificial intelligence in self-driving cars, was delivered by a candidate from the Université Bourgogne Europe.

This event was livestreamed to the wider FORTHEM community, enabling a transnational audience to participate by voting online. Approximately 672 unique viewers joined from across Europe, with localized viewing groups in Finland, Poland, Latvia, Germany, Romania, and France. In total, 50 PhD candidates were involved in the national or local RGP activities, and 11 were selected for the European final. Five universities hosted local finals.

The RGP format was adopted with flexibility to accommodate existing local science communication traditions. For instance, Mainz used its established Science Slam format (10 minutes), requiring finalists to adapt their presentation to the RGP's shorter format for the final. Institutions such as the University of Opole and the University of Latvia followed the Norwegian format more closely. To support the process, the University of Agder provided extensive mentoring, including online "coaching for coaches" and dissemination of practical guidelines.

A significant challenge lay in preparing participants to communicate not only to a national audience but to a broader European public. To address this, an intensive two-day coaching session was held prior to the international final. Presentations were repeatedly rehearsed and assessed across three core dimensions: content clarity and relevance, visual support, and delivery style. A language coach supported participants, ensuring comprehensibility despite the fact that none were native English speakers. This process fostered a sense of community among participants, who supported each other across disciplinary and national boundaries.

The RGP has demonstrated measurable impact in enhancing the communication competencies of early-stage researchers (ESRs). Participants not only gained practical experience in public speaking but also reported increased confidence in presenting their work to general audiences. As one participant from Mainz reflected: "This was a great experience, and it was really cool to be part of FORTHEM Researcher Grand Prix and meet PhD colleagues from all over Europe".

The skills gained are particularly relevant in the context of employability. Effective science communication has been identified as a key transferable skill that increases career mobility within and beyond academia. According to participant from University of Latvia: “For us researchers it’s necessary to get the right tools so we are able to present our research for a broader audience”. Also, in the eyes of one of the coordinators of this event, this kind of experience is relevant: “I’ve seen a great development among the participants. From participating locally at each university to being here in Kristiansand and gaining confidence and sharpening their communication skills through practice. This is a fantastic opportunity for our PhD candidates which they otherwise wouldn’t have gotten”³⁶.

Following the success of the first international edition, further expansion is already planned. In 2025, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu (Romania), the University of Valencia (Spain), and the University of Palermo (Italy) will join the initiative. The final will be hosted in Dijon, France.

The Researchers Grand Prix initiative within FORTHEM Alliance illustrates how structured training in science communication can foster both individual development and cross-border collaboration among early-career researchers. By emphasizing public engagement and interdisciplinary exchange, the program contributes meaningfully to the broader mission of enhancing the societal impact of academic research.

Mentoring program

FORTHEM Mentoring Programme was designed to support the professional development and employability of ESRs within FORTHEM Alliance. Inspired by existing models—particularly the mentoring approach developed at the University of Jyväskylä (JYU)—the programme aims to foster academic growth through regular, structured, yet flexible peer and expert interaction³⁷. The JYU model emphasizes group mentoring with regular meetings over the course of an academic year. It brings together doctoral students, experienced researchers and a few master-degree students in a supportive, interdisciplinary setting, encouraging open discussions around academic careers, research practices, and transferable skills.

Following this approach, FORTHEM Mentoring Programme includes both group and individual mentoring formats, matching, when possible, participants based on their academic background, level of experience, and preferred topics of interest. Each round of mentoring runs for approximately one

³⁶ A.M. Larsen, AI in self-driving cars won the FORTHEM Researcher Grand Prix. Accessed 25 August 2025 on <https://www.uia.no/english/about-uia/news/forthem-researcher-grand-prix.html>

³⁷ FORTHEM Milestone MS30: *Mentoring Programme*. Document has a sensitive dissemination level, and is available on reasonable request.

year and is designed to be flexible: groups are self-directed, with suggested monthly meetings lasting between 60 and 90 minutes. English is used as the common language, although groups can choose other languages depending on participants' preferences. The programme includes a kick-off meeting to launch it and a joint bootcamp, offering participants an opportunity to learn about FORTHEM opportunities, share experiences, attend targeted training, and explore further networking opportunities.

The first cohort of FORTHEM Mentoring Programme took place between March 2024 and March 2025. A total of 29 mentors and 64 mentees applied to participate. However, only 10 mentors and 22 mentees remained active throughout the full programme, and 10 mentoring groups submitted final reports. Despite a strong start, approximately 65% of participants withdrew during the programme. The main reasons included scheduling conflicts, dissatisfaction with the mentor-mentee match, and a lack of commitment. Some participants stopped replying to emails, while others communicated their decision to leave. Mentors were also affected, and in a few cases, they abandoned their groups during the process. Given the limited results, task manager introduced, for the first cohort, a training meeting, which was mandatory to participate as mentor and to be included in the matching. Nevertheless, the second cohort had the same problems, so, the manager proposed to enhance participant engagement in the final cohort, organizing the last mentoring bootcamp as a Blended Intensive Programme (BIP).

Nevertheless, the feedback from those who completed the programme was highly positive. Participants reported significant improvements in academic writing, research methodology, and public presentation skills. Many also gained a deeper understanding of academic publishing. Tangible outcomes included completed research proposals, student-driven projects, peer-reviewed publications, meeting in presence through short-term mobilities and participation in conferences.

Participants particularly appreciated the international and interdisciplinary nature of the programme, which allowed them to learn from peers in other countries and research fields. The informal structure gave groups the freedom to define their own goals and meeting topics, leading to a strong sense of ownership and engagement. In terms of impact, the programme supports the employability of early-stage researchers by helping them build essential academic and transferable skills. These include project planning, time management, intercultural communication, and teamwork—competencies that are increasingly important in both academic and non-academic careers. Literature on research training and career development has long emphasized the value of mentoring in building confidence,

broadening professional networks, and accelerating career progression³⁸. Acting as a mentor also benefits postdoctoral researchers, giving them early experience in teaching, supervision, and leadership—key abilities for future academic roles.

Research Assessment Reform – Our Actions

FORTHEM is actively contributing to the key ideas of the **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA³⁹)**, a European initiative to reform how research and researchers are evaluated.

- **Aim:** Move beyond narrow metrics (e.g. impact factor) toward qualitative, fair, and inclusive evaluations.
- **Focus:** Recognize diverse outputs such as open science, teamwork, and societal impact.
- **Timeline:** Published July 20, 2022; open for signature since September 28, 2022.
- **Commitment:** Signatories develop a reform action plan within one year and join the CoARA coalition.

Eight FORTHEM partner universities have signed the agreement; so far, the University of Palermo, Jyväskylä University, University of Agder, and Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz have submitted dedicated action plans, either individually or as part of a consortium.

Based on the results of **FIT FORTHEM** project, the Alliance conducted an in-depth analysis of research assessment procedures across partner universities, aligning with the European Commission's objectives and the **CoARA Agreement**. In 2023–2024, surveys involving 268 researchers—especially Early-Stage Researchers—revealed strong support (70%) for qualitative, inclusive assessment methods, but also highlighted low awareness, uneven implementation, and disciplinary differences. Universities have begun implementing action plans, collaborating nationally and within CoARA, while a dedicated FORTHEM expert group engaging about 25 experts from partner universities works to share best practices, agree on indicators, and explore innovations such as Open Science recognition, transfer activities, and narrative CVs.

The main recommendations from the surveys and expert exchanges are to engage research communities in the reform process, link research assessment reforms with the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers, strengthen training and communication, combine quantitative and qualitative methods tailored to disciplines, develop institutional action plans aligned with national

³⁸ Johnson, M. O., & Gandhi, M. (2015). A mentor training program improves mentoring competency for researchers working with early-career investigators from underrepresented backgrounds. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 20(3), 683-689.

³⁹ [CoARA – Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (access 15.8.2025)

frameworks, collaborate with national and international stakeholders, and promote peer learning. Funders and authorities are urged to provide clear guidelines, incentives, and accountability to drive genuine reform and reduce reliance on outdated metrics, with FORTHEM committed to fostering fairer, more inclusive research cultures across Europe. Looking ahead to the next funding period, FORTHEM will use these insights to better coordinate and align approaches across partners, ensuring greater coherence and shared impact in future reforms.

An in-depth analysis of survey results, policy developments and exchanges of the expert group was provided to the top-level management of partner universities for further action.

Supporting Early-Stage Researcher Careers in FORTHEM through Third-Party Funding

FORTHEM alliance, uniting nine universities across Europe, provides a distinctive environment to strengthen the careers of early-stage researchers (ESRs) – particularly doctoral candidates and postdoctoral fellows – by strategically mobilizing third-party funding. By aligning European and national funding instruments with the different stages of academic careers, external grants can be systematically translated into structured career advancement.

In 2024, a group of experts from both the work package and institutional levels convened in Mainz to design a structural framework aimed at establishing sustainable funding pathways. This framework seeks not only to support individual talent development and cross-alliance mobility at all stages of academic careers, but also to foster joint research agendas and collaborative projects, building on the foundations laid in the FIT FORTHEM project and further expanded in the current funding period.

While such structural measures are essential, individual ESRs also require personalized guidance in shaping their own career strategies. The ability to successfully apply for third-party funding is itself a key professional skill, enabling researchers to actively design their career trajectories. To make opportunities more transparent and navigable, FORTHEM proposes the introduction of a Funding Ladder, which systematically maps available schemes at successive career stages (see Table: Funding Ladder for Early-Stage Researchers). This ladder integrates both European programmes—such as the MSCA Doctoral Networks, Postdoctoral Fellowships, ERC Starting Grants, COST Actions, and Widening schemes—and national-level opportunities across the FORTHEM countries. By presenting these in a single framework, researchers are better able to identify suitable instruments, align them with their career stage, and strategically plan their academic development.

To turn these opportunities into structured and accessible career pathways, FORTHEM could implement the following measures:

- Publication of Funding Ladders by discipline, with clear deadlines and mobility requirements.
- Alliance-wide training clinics for MSCA Doctoral Networks, Postdoctoral Fellowships, and ERC Starting Grants, including peer review support.
- Seed funding for consortia, enabling applications for MSCA DN and Widening projects.
- A Seal of Excellence support track, providing personalized coaching for resubmissions.

By matching funding instruments to career stages, exploiting mobility opportunities, and leveraging FORTHEM’s geographical and institutional diversity to build strong consortia, early-stage researchers will be able to accelerate their careers while strengthening the alliance’s collective research capacity. In this way, FORTHEM not only enhances individual academic trajectories, but also reinforces its role as a dynamic and sustainable actor within the European Research Area.

Tab. 2: Funding Ladder for Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs)

Career Stage	Core EU Instruments	National Opportunities (FORTHEM Countries)
Doctoral Stage	- MSCA Doctoral Networks (mobility, secondments)	- National doctoral grants
Late PhD / Early Postdoc	- COST Actions (training schools, networking, WG leadership) - Seal of Excellence (for strong MSCA proposals)	- NCN ETIUDA / SONATINA (Poland) - AEI Juan de la Cierva (Spain) - DFG Walter Benjamin Programme (Germany) - Research Council of Finland Postdoctoral Grants - Latvian Postdoctoral Grants
2–5 years post-PhD	- MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships (12–24 months in EU; global fellowships with return phase)	- ANR JCJC (France) - SONATA (Poland) - PRIN (Italy) - National Young PI schemes
3–7 years post-PhD	- ERC Starting Grants (prestigious early PI track) - Widening Actions (Twinning, Teaming, ERA Chairs)	- ATIP-Avenir (France) - Ramón y Cajal (Spain) - FRIPRO Young Talents (Norway) - UEFISCDI TE Young Teams (Romania) - DFG Emmy Noether Programme (Germany) - Alexander von Humboldt Research Fellowship (Germany) - Academy Research Fellow (Finland)

Results

The activities of FORTHEM Academy for Early-Stage Researchers (FA4ESR) must be understood against the broader context of structural challenges identified across the European Research Area. As outlined in the diagnostic section of this report, early-stage researchers (ESRs) continue to face precarious employment conditions, fragmented career pathways, unequal recognition of doctoral and postdoctoral status across Member States, and persistent gender disparities in career progression.

Within this environment, FA4ESR has delivered concrete practices that partially mitigate these systemic barriers. By providing structured training in transferable skills, open science, and competitive funding schemes, the Academy has responded directly to the widespread need for greater preparedness for both academic and non-academic labour markets. Activities such as the MSCA MasterClass and online workshops have addressed the lack of institutionalised grant-writing and career-development support noted in many national contexts.

Equally, FA4ESR's mentoring programme and cross-border mobility schemes, while challenged by high dropout rates and varying national regulations, highlighted the systemic obstacles that doctoral and postdoctoral researchers face when seeking international exposure. The lessons drawn from these difficulties are themselves valuable results, providing evidence of the need for more flexible and inclusive mobility policies at the European level.

Moreover, the Academy's commitment to gender equality and inclusive research assessment reform reflects the ERA's priorities while addressing persistent inequalities diagnosed earlier in this report. Initiatives such as *FORTHEM Journal* and the Researchers' Grand Prix have created visible platforms where ESRs—particularly women and underrepresented groups—can demonstrate leadership and gain recognition often lacking in conventional academic hierarchies.

Overall, the results of FA4ESR can be summarised as proof-of-concept interventions: while they do not eliminate structural precarity, they provide workable models that align with ERA ambitions and respond to the key deficits identified in the diagnostic analysis.

Impact and Policy Recommendations

Short-term impact (1–2 years)

- Boosted employability of Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) through structured grant-writing, project design and science-communication training (e.g., MSCA MasterClass, online workshops).
- Operational mentoring cohorts with clearer onboarding, expectations and hybrid meeting formats to reduce drop-out.
- Pilots of narrative CVs and recognition of Open Science, teamwork and transfer activities in assessment at partner universities.
- Short and hybrid mobility offers aligned with family-friendly policies and administrative clarity (social security, visas).

Medium-term impact (3–5 years)

- Institutionalisation of transferable-skills provision in doctoral/postdoctoral training across all partners (from ad hoc to embedded curricula).
- Alliance-wide minimum standards for ESR status (contracts, rights, benefits) to reduce disparities between countries and units.
- Coordinated research assessment reform (CoARA-aligned) across partners, including Open Science recognition and narrative elements.
- Scaled open-science communication platforms (FORTHEM Journal, Researchers' Grand Prix) improving visibility and inclusion.

Long-term impact (5–10 years)

- Greater attractiveness and stability of research careers across the ERA, with interoperable, comparable ESR frameworks.
- Measurable narrowing of gender gaps at senior levels via monitored equality plans and incentives.
- Stronger intersectoral mobility and knowledge valorisation via sustained skills provision, mobility and assessment reforms.
- Evidence base and pilots informing FP10, Erasmus+ and national reforms on careers, mobility and assessment.

Stakeholder-specific recommendations

Table 3: FORTHEM Alliance & Partner Universities

Recommendation	Responsible actor(s)	Time horizon
Harmonise ESR status via shared minimum standards (contracts, rights, benefits).	FORTHEM Steering Committee; Rectors;	3–5 years
Embed transferable skills training structurally in doctoral/postdoctoral curricula.	Graduate/Doctoral Schools; Vice-Rectors for Education	1–2 years
Adapt mobility to short/hybrid formats (family-friendly, admin support).	International Offices; Project Offices	1–2 years
Strengthen gender equality monitoring and targeted support at transition points.	Equality & Diversity Offices; Departments	1–3 years
Institutionalise mentoring, Open Science and communication (Journal, RGP).	Graduate Schools; Communication Units	1–3 years

Table 4: Policymakers & Funders (EU, national, regional)

Recommendation	Responsible actor(s)	Time horizon
Establish an EU framework for ESR status and rights (employee recognition, social protection, transparent postdoctoral pathways).	European Commission (DG RTD/EMPL); Council; Member States	3–5 years
Mandate transferable-skills components in EU-funded doctoral/postdoctoral programmes.	European Commission; Agencies (REA/EACEA)	1–2 years
Promote flexible mobility (short/hybrid) in Horizon Europe & Erasmus+ with simplified administration.	European Commission; EACEA; National Agencies	1–3 years
Embed CoARA-aligned assessment principles in funding and evaluation.	EU & national funders; Research Councils	1–3 years
Use FP10/Erasmus+/Competitiveness instruments to incentivise structural change (careers, equality, intersectoral mobility).	European Commission; Member States	3–7 years

References

1. Official and Institutional Documents

Council of the European Union. 2021. Council conclusions on the European Universities initiative – Bridging higher education, research, innovation and society. OJ C 221, 10 June 2021. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C:2021:221:TOC>

Council Recommendation (EU) 2021/2122 of 26 November 2021 on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe. OJ L 431, 2 Dec 2021, 1–9. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2021/2122/oj>

Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 of 2 December 2022 on the guiding principles for knowledge valorisation. OJ L 317, 9 Dec 2022, 141–148. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2022/2415/oj>

Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023 on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe. C/2023/1640. OJ C 29/2023. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/C/2023/1640/oj/eng>

European Commission. 2000. Communication from the Commission: Towards a European Research Area. COM (2000) 6 final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52000DC0006>

Commission Recommendation of 11 March 2005 on the European Charter for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. 2005/251/EC. OJ L 75, 22 Mar 2005, 67–77. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32005H0251>

Towards a European Framework for Research Careers. EURAXESS Policy Library. https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/policy_library/towards_a_european_framework_for_research_careers_final.pdf

A New ERA for Research and Innovation. COM (2020) 628 final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628>

A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025. COM (2020) 152 final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0152>

European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience. COM (2020) 274 final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0274>

A New European Innovation Agenda. COM (2022) 332 final. Brussels. https://commission.europa.eu/publications/new-european-innovation-agenda_en

Attracting Skills and Talent to the EU. COM (2022) 657 final. Brussels. https://commission.europa.eu/publications/attracting-skills-and-talent-eu_en

Communication on a European Strategy for Universities. COM (2022) 16 final. Brussels.
https://commission.europa.eu/publications/communication-european-strategy-universities_en

Harnessing Talent in Europe's Regions. COM (2023) 32 final. Brussels.
https://commission.europa.eu/publications/harnessing-talent-europes-regions_en

Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe. COM (2023) 436 final. Brussels. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu>

ResearchComp — The European Competence Framework for Researchers. Brussels: DG Research & Innovation. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchers/research-competence-framework-researchers_en

Proposal for a Regulation establishing the Erasmus+ programme. COM (2025) 549 final. CELEX 52025PC0549. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52025PC0549>

Proposal for a Regulation establishing the European Competitiveness Fund. COM (2025) 555 final. CELEX 52025PC0555. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52025PC0555>

She Figures 2024: Gender in Research and Innovation. Publications Office of the EU. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7646222f-e82b-11ef-b5e9-01aa75ed71a1>

European Parliament and Council. 2016. Directive (EU) 2016/801 of 11 May 2016 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for research, studies, training, voluntary service, pupil exchange schemes or educational projects and au pairing. OJ L 132, 21 May 2016, 21–57. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/801/oj>

2021. Directive (EU) 2021/1883 of 20 October 2021 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purpose of highly qualified employment (recast). OJ L 382, 28 Oct 2021, 1–38. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2021/1883/oj>

2. Academic Literature

Agathokleous, E. 2021. “Engaging in Scientific Peer Review: Tips for Young Reviewers.” *Journal of Forestry Research* 32(6): 2249–2254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-020-01262-1>

Bojica, A. M., J. Olmos-Peñuela, and J. Alegre. 2023. “A Cross-country Configurational Approach to International Academic Mobility: Exploring Mobility Effects on Academics’ Career Progression in EU Countries.” *Higher Education* 86(5): 1081–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-022-00963-0>

Boman, J., M. Sanchez Barrioluengo, and I. van der Weijden. 2025. “Determinants of the Career Pathways of Doctorate Holders: Evidence from Eight European Universities.” *Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-025-01418-y>

Hnátková, E., I. Degtyarova, M. Kersschot, and J. Boman. 2022. "Labour Market Perspectives for PhD Graduates in Europe." *European Journal of Education* 57(3): 395–409. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12514>

Janger, J., D. F. J. Campbell, and A. Strauss. 2019. "Attractiveness of Jobs in Academia: A Cross-country Perspective." *Higher Education* 78: 991–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-019-00376-1>

Johnson, M. O., and M. Gandhi. 2015. "A Mentor Training Program Improves Mentoring Competency for Researchers Working with Early-career Investigators from Underrepresented Backgrounds." *Advances in Health Sciences Education* 20(3): 683–689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10459-014-9555-z>

Machado, H. P. V., R. Sartori, and P. F. M. Rosa. 2024. "Beyond the Triple Helix Model: Scientific Production on the Quadruple and Quintuple Helix." *Journal of the Knowledge Economy* 16: 5758–5791. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-02026-4>

Marshall, H., and M. Fernandes. 2021. "Early-career Researchers Shaping Publishing Strategy." *Learned Publishing* 34(4): 675–678. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1381>

Molek-Kozakowska, K., and R. Geisler. 2020. "De-bureaucratising Organisational Culture at a Public University: A Mixed-method Study of the Implementation of a Liberal Arts Programme." *Higher Education Quarterly* 74(2): 144–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12262>

Nicholas, D., H. R. Jamali, C. Tenopir, R. Volentine, E. Herman, R. Watkinson, and K. Levine. 2015. "Do Younger Researchers Assess Trustworthiness Differently When Deciding What to Read and Cite? The Effect of Age on Citing Behaviour." *Information Research* 20(3): paper 687. <http://informationr.net/ir/20-3/paper687.html>

Torrisi, B. 2016. "Asymmetric Salary and Uniformity of Academic Positions at Universities in the EU28." *Open Access Library Journal* 3: e03198. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1103198>

Zayim-Kurtay, M., S. Kaya-Kasikci, and Y. Kondakci. 2025. "Im/mobility in a Disruptive Time: The Impact of Covid-19 on the Size and Directional Flow of International Student Mobility." *Comparative Migration Studies* 13(15). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-025-00431-5>

Zuba, K. 2025. *Europeanisation as an Opportunity Structure*. In: A. Frame, B. Curyło (eds.) *The European Universities Initiative and the 'Euro-Internationalisation' of European Higher Education*. Routledge, 2025.

3. Reports, Statistics, Rankings

EUA Council for Doctoral Education (Hasgall, A., Saenen, B., Borrell-Damian, L., et al.). 2020. *Doctoral Education in Europe Today: Approaches and Institutional Structures*. Brussels: EUA-CDE.

EUA Council for Doctoral Education (Marti, S., and A.-M. Peneoasu). 2025. *Doctoral Education in Europe Today: Enhanced Structures and Practices for the European Knowledge Society*. Brussels: EUA-CDE.

European Commission, DG Research & Innovation. 2020. MORE4 Final Report: Support Data Collection and Analysis Concerning Mobility Patterns and Career Paths of Researchers. Brussels. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3a82f01a-5a08-11eb-b487-01aa75ed71a1>

European University Association, Council for Doctoral Education (EUA-CDE). 2025. Doctoral Education in Europe Today: Results of the 2025 EUA-CDE Survey (Part 1). Brussels: EUA-CDE.

Eurostat. 2024. “Women totalled almost a third of STEM graduates in 2021.” Eurostat News Release, 8 March 2024. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20240308-1>

Informations und Mobilitätsverhalten. 2017. Eine weltweite Befragung internationaler Nachwuchswissenschaftler. Schriftenreihe Hochschulmarketing, DAAD. Bonn: DAAD.

OECD. 2019. Benchmarking Higher Education System Performance. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/be5514d7-en>

OECD. 2021. Reducing the Precarity of Academic Research Careers. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 113. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1ab39bdc-en>

OECD. 2024. The State of Academic Careers in OECD Countries — An Evidence Review. OECD Education Policy Perspectives No. 91. Paris: OECD Publishing.

Science Europe. 2021. Research Culture: Empowering Researchers with a Thriving Research System (Statement). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726893>

ShanghaiRanking Consultancy. 2024. Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU) 2024. <http://www.shanghairanking.com>

4. Web and Internal Sources

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). 2022. Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. <https://www.coara.eu/agreement>

EURAXESS. 2011–2025. EURAXESS — Researchers in Motion: mobility and careers resources. <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu>

FORTHEM Alliance. 2024. MS30: Mentoring Programme — Milestone report. Internal project document (available on request).

University of Agder (UiA). 2024. “FORTHEM Researcher Grand Prix.” UiA News. <https://www.uia.no/english/about-uia/news/forthem-researcher-grand-prix.html>

Vitae. n.d. Researcher Development Framework (RDF). <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-rdf>

YUFE Alliance. n.d. YUFE: Hands-on training on Open Science — H2020 fact sheet / training concept. Horizon 2020 / YUFE portal.